

Synthesis of high alumina ZSM-5 molecular sieve with ethylene diamine as template

N. Venkatathri

Catalysis Division, National Chemical Laboratory, Pune-411 008, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : venkat@cata.ncl.res.in Fax : 91-20-25893761

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Abstract : Attempts were made to investigate compositional constraints in the synthesis of pentasil molecular sieves, including aluminosilicate zeolites using ethylene diamine (C₂DN) template, from the gel composition 1.85Na₂O : aAl₂O₃ : 15.2SiO₂ : 592H₂O : 19.7C₂DN in the temperature 177 °C for ten days. When $a = 0.25$ the product was ZSM-5 and then $a = 1$ the product was ZSM-35 and in between compositions the mixture of two were obtained. Reduce the time of crystallization time to 5 days give nanocrystalline material. XRD and FT-IR spectra in framework region of ZSM-5 synthesized using ethylene diamine template and without template are having similar pattern, however the intensity varies. Scanning electron microscopic picture of the both are varies. The structural stability of the zeolite ZSM-5 synthesized using no template was also found to be lower as compared with that for the ZSM-5 synthesized using ethylene diamine template. These differences may result from the occluded excess sodium.

Keywords : Molecular sieve, zeolite, ethylenediamine.

Argauer and Landolt¹ of Mobil Oil Corporation, in 1972, obtained the first patent on the synthesis of a pentasil aluminosilicate zeolite, termed ZSM-5 and described as having SiO₂/Al₂O₃ = 5–100 as a broad range, by using quaternary ammonium compounds (TPA-Br/TPAOH) as templating agents. Other pentasil molecular sieves, with SiO₂/Al₂O₃ ≥ 200 have also been described^{2,3}. Since then, considerable literature has developed on the synthesis of these molecular sieves by using a wide variety of quaternary ammonium compounds^{4,5}, amines⁶, and other organic compounds⁷ as templates. Recently ethylene diamine was reported to crystallize rapidly, high silica ZSM-5 material^{8,9}. However there is no reports on high alumina or low silica ZSM-5. The role of organic structure-directing agents has been discussed¹⁰ as have the kinetics of complex processes such as nucleation and crystallization¹¹. Both solid-phase and liquid phase transformations have been proposed¹¹ as possible mechanisms of the crystallization of these zeolites. Until recently, the templating species were thought to be essential in the synthesis. Attempts have been made to synthesize these molecular sieves without amine templating agents but in the presence of methylethyl ketone¹², methanol/ethanol¹³, acetone¹⁴, and/or seed crystals¹⁵. In many cases the products obtained were of lower degree of crystallinity or were phases other than ZSM-5. Although several nontemplate or additive synthesis have been reported to synthesis ZSM-5 in the patent literature^{16–19} and in the open literature^{20–26} the products consisted unreacted amorphous solid or quartz or coexisted with

mordenite or analcime. It was therefore thought worth while to examine the possible synthesis of low silica ZSM-5 using ethylene diamine and without any template. The results are reported here.

Results and discussion

To determine the compositional range of the hydrogel that would yield a pentasil molecular sieve, synthesis runs were carried out from the hydrogel system whose oxide mole composition was 1.85Na₂O : aAl₂O₃ : 15.2SiO₂ : 592H₂O : 19.7C₂DN at 177 °C. The value of "a" was varied from 0.25 to <1 The crystallization time was fixed at 5–10 days. Table 1 summarizing the different phases obtained from the present system, indicates that ZSM-5, ZSM-5 + ZSM-35 and ZSM-35 are the main phases identified in the present study. Table 1 shows that the pure ZSM-5 phase was obtained with $a = 0.25$. At 0.5 major phases obtained was ZSM-5 and ZSM-35 and at high alumina contents the major phase obtained was ZSM-35. It has been reported⁵ that, in the case of ZSM-5 synthesis from template containing systems, the time required to obtain a 100% crystalline product decreases with increase in SiO₂/Al₂O₃. The opposite trend is however apparent in the present template free system.

The different phases (tabulated in Table 1) obtained during the present synthetic studies are identified on the basis of their X-ray diffraction pattern. Fig. 1d shows a typical

XRD pattern take at 8°/min scan for the product obtained gel composition 1.85Na₂O : 0.25Al₂O₃ : 15.2SiO₂ : 592H₂O : 19.7C₂DN crystallized at 177 °C for 10 days. This X-ray pattern characterizes the product to be almost pure ZSM-5. The sample prepared was step scanned with an internal standard. The results are shown in Table 2 and compared to a pattern for ZSM-5 prepared without template. It is seen that the agreement is excellent, indicating complete crystallization had occurred. The elemental composition are given in Table 1. All the molecular sieves are having Si/Al ratio, lower than the input amount.

Table 1 Various gel compositions used to synthesis aluminosilicates

Sample code	Gel composition	Time	Temp (°C)	Template	Si/Al (Product)	Product
A	1.85Na ₂ O Al ₂ O ₃ 15.2SiO ₂ 592H ₂ O 19.7C ₂ DN	10 days	177	Ethylene diamine	10	ZSM-35
B	1.85Na ₂ O Al ₂ O ₃ 15.2SiO ₂ 592H ₂ O 19.7C ₂ DN	5 days	177	Ethylene diamine	15	Nano-crystalline ZSM-35
C	1.85Na ₂ O 0.5Al ₂ O ₃ 15.2SiO ₂ 592H ₂ O 19.7C ₂ DN	10 days	177	Ethylene diamine	35	ZSM-5 + ZSM-35
D	1.85Na ₂ O 0.25Al ₂ O ₃ 15.2SiO ₂ 592H ₂ O 19.7C ₂ DN	10 days	177	Ethylene diamine	70	ZSM-5
E	40SiO ₂ Al ₂ O ₃ 4.5Na ₂ O 1300H ₂ O	40 h	150	Nil	25	ZSM-5

C₂DN = Ethylene diamine

Scanning electron micrographs of ZSM-35 conversion to ZSM-5 on varying aluminium content were given in Fig. 2 and correlate with the XRD patterns of Fig. 1. The crystal habit of the ZSM-5 crystals synthesized using no template seems to be rather different to that observed with the crystal synthesized using organic templates. However, Fig. 2d and e showing intergrown platelets (ZSM-5 from diethylamine) crystals and spheroid sieves (ZSM-5 without tem-

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of (a) ZSM-35, (b) nanocrystalline ZSM-35, (c) ZSM-35 + ZSM-5, (d) ZSM-5 (ethylene diamine) and (e) ZSM-5 (without template)

plate) with the uniform size, indicates that the product is of high purity and it is not contaminated with impurity phases.

Fig. 3 shows the thermogravimetric and differential thermometric curves for both the ZSM-5 samples synthesized in the absence and presence of an organic template (ethylene diamine). Curve a represents the templated sample showing a distinct step for a loss in weight (8.59%) around 130–661 °C, which is due to decomposition of the template. The total % loss in weight for this sample is 13.11. Curve c, for ZSM-5 sample prepared without template, shows a continuous loss in weight up to 621 °C amounting to 10.92%. The entire loss in weight is due to removal of water from the zeolite cavity. Both sample when calcined up to 823 K and allowed to cool to room temperature were found to absorb ~12.5% water on equilibrating at room temperature. This indicates that sample synthesized without template shows reversible dehydration with almost the same pore volume as that of ZSM-5 synthesized using an organic template (ethylene diamine).

The main difference between the two TG/DTA (ZSM-35 and Nanocrystalline ZSM-35) is that the nanocrystalline

Fig. 2. Scanning electron microscopic picture of (a) ZSM-35, (b) nanocrystalline ZSM-35, (c) ZSM-35 + ZSM-5 (ethylene diamine) and (e) ZSM-5 (without template)

samples were loose all the template in two steps, the first endothermic loss at 103 °C (7.42% loss) is due to the loss of physisorbed template and water the second exothermic step at 325 °C (3.69% loss) is due to the oxidative decomposition of the template. As the particle size is small the decomposition is easier in this case. Whereas ZSM-35 samples loss in five stages. In the low temperature region up to 586 K, endothermic weight loss occurs in two stages (6.56% and 1.88%) mainly due to the loss of adsorbed water and template. In the temperature region of 586 to 1086 K, there are three stages of exothermic weight loss (1.41, 4.22 and 3.59% respectively) due to the oxidative decomposition of the organic template occluded in the sample. The probable oxidation stages as follows : in the 586–642 K region occluded template molecules in the pores oxidatively decompose with burning of a part of the hydrocarbon, while in the region 642–817 K, protonated template molecules interacting strongly with the framework charge and the fragments

of templates decomposed and adsorbed at lower temperatures are partially oxidized leaving behind a coke residue. In the last stage (817–1086 K), this coke is eliminated by oxidation. Based on the total loss due to template removal and the carbon and nitrogen analysis (2.21%C, 2.04%N for nanocrystalline ZSM-35, and 4.40%C, 4.15%N for ZSM-35) it is estimated that three ethylene diamine molecules are occluded in each unit cell of ZSM-35 where as the same reduced to half in nanocrystalline ZSM-35.

The main difference between the two TG/DTA is that the ZSM-35 + ZSM-5 and ZSM-5 samples were loose all the template in two steps, the first endothermic loss at 103 °C (4.0 and 4.42% loss) is due to the loss of physisorbed template and water the second exothermic step at 325 °C (10 and 8.69% loss) is due to the oxidative decomposition of the template. Whereas ZSM-35 samples loss in five stages. In the low temperature region up to 586 K, endothermic weight loss occurs in two stages (6.56% and 1.88%) mainly due to the loss of adsorbed water and template. In the temperature region of 586 to 1086 K, there are three stages of exothermic weight loss (1.41, 4.22 and 3.59% respectively) due to the oxidative decomposition of the organic template occluded in the sample. The probable oxidation stages as follows : in the 586–642 K region occluded template molecules in the pores oxidatively decompose with burning of a part of the hydrocarbon, while in the region 642–817 K, protonated template molecules interacting strongly with the framework charge and the fragments of templates decomposed and adsorbed at lower temperatures are partially oxidized leaving behind a coke residue. In the last stage (817–1086 K), this coke is eliminated by oxidation. Based on the total loss due to template removal and the carbon and nitrogen analysis (4.40%C, 4.15%N for ZSM-35, 4.71%C, 4.24%N for ZSM-35 + ZSM-5 and 4.69%C, 3.16%N for ZSM-5) it is estimated that three ethylene diamine molecules are occluded in each unit cell of all the aluminosilicates. However, the template content is decreased when going from ZSM-35 to ZSM-5.

The XRD patterns of both ZSM-5 samples after carrying out TG analysis upto 1193 K. It is seen that the XRD pattern for ZSM-5 sample 'a' has retained almost full crystallinity. The lower peak heights appearance of new reflections and the absence of some of the peaks for ZSM-5 in the XRD pattern of sample 'b' indicates a loss in crystallinity and the beginning of a phase change. This suggests that although ZSM-5 can be synthesized successfully from or-

ganic template free systems, the zeolite so synthesized under our conditions exhibits rather lower framework rigidity or structural stability as compared with that exhibited by ZSM-5 synthesized using an organic template. The observation is similar to that reported by Berak and Mostowicz²⁷

Fig. 3. TG (b,d)/DTA(a,c) analysis of ZSM-5 synthesized (a,b) with template and (c,d) without template

The infrared spectrum in the framework region (400–4000 cm^{-1}) for NaZSM-5 ($\text{SiO}_2/\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 40$) synthesized using no organic template and ethylene diamine template are shown in Fig 4. The absorption bands at 420, 534, 788 and 1089 cm^{-1} are assigned²⁸ for external linkages and in accordance with Raman spectroscopy, the bands at 330, 350, 770 and 1090 cm^{-1} are found²⁸ to be exhibited by the variation mode of the skeletal framework. The strong absorption band in the region 1000–1200 cm^{-1} has been assigned²⁹ to the internal vibrations of SiO_4 , AlO_4 tetrahedra for ZSM-5, and also for silica and quartz. The absorption at around 450 cm^{-1} was assigned by Jacobs *et al*³⁰ to a highly distorted double five membered ring present in the zeolite framework. The absorbance band near 1200 cm^{-1} was assigned⁴ to the asymmetric stretching vibration of the T-O linkage. A strong band at 789 cm^{-1} seems to be not split into a doublet as reported earlier²¹. The shoulders at 667 and 590 cm^{-1} and a band at 534 cm^{-1} shift to a higher frequency at 690, 610 and 548 cm^{-1} respectively. A strong band at 1090 cm^{-1} has shifted to higher frequency at 1101 cm^{-1} . The band at 667 cm^{-1} is however found to be comparatively weaker.

Fig. 4. FT-IR spectra of ZSM-5 synthesized (a) with template and (b) without template

Table 2. Comparison of XRD pattern for ZSM-5 prepared without template with template pattern

Pattern with ethylene diamine template		Pattern without template	
d (Å)	hkl	d (Å)	hkl
11.53	22	11.35	15
10.30	18	10.08	33
9.12	7	–	–
6.49	5	6.37	10
6.10	6	6.07	10
5.82	6	–	–
5.66	6	–	–
5.07	5	5.06	15
4.67	6	–	–
4.42	8	4.40	12
4.32	14	4.29	19
4.13	12	4.16	17
4.03	12	4.07	14
3.88	100	3.86	100
3.77	49	3.75	50
3.69	31	3.67	24
3.57	10	–	–
3.50	15	–	–
3.34	12	3.27	24
3.16	6	3.23	23
3.07	14	3.06	20
3.01	17	3.00	21
2.75	5	2.86	12
2.62	6	–	–
2.51	10	–	–
2.41	6	2.43	15
2.02	16	2.02	20
2.00	19	2.00	18
1.92	9	–	–
1.88	7	1.85	27

The FTIR spectrum of the as-synthesized ZSM-35, ZSM-35 + ZSM-5 and ZSM-5 in the framework region gives bands for the different modes of tetrahedral linkages give bands at 1232(sh), 1062(vs), 1208(sh), 797(s), 696(w), 581(s), 528(sh), 460(sh), 424(s) cm^{-1} . The bands can be assigned to asymmetric stretching, symmetric stretching, pore

opening, double ring and bending vibrations of T-O-T linkages described in earlier literature. The 534 cm^{-1} peaks are sharper in ZSM-35 + ZSM-5 and ZSM-5 samples

Experimental

In a typical procedure to synthesize ZSM-5 using ethylene diamine template, 0.825 g of sodium aluminate (99%, s.d. fine, India) was mixed well with 0.7 g of sodium hydroxide (99%, s.d. fine, India) and 129 g of distilled water. This mixture was stirred well until all the solid is dissolved. This was taken as solution A. Another solution B was made by thorough mixing of 46.47 g of silica sol (30%, s.d. fine, India) and ethylene diamine (18.3 g, 99%, Aldrich, USA). Solutions A and B were mixed well to make clear mixture and charged into a teflon lined steel autoclave. Crystallization was carried out at $177\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 10 days. Experiments were conducted with varying aluminium content by keeping the remaining components constant.

In a typical experiment to synthesis ZSM-5 without template, 40 g Ludox (30%, s.d. fine, India), was diluted with 60 ml deionized water to get solution A. Sodium hydroxide, 1.2 g (99%, s.d. fine, India) was dissolved in 47 ml of water. Pseudo-Boehmite, 0.345 g (74.2%, Vista Chemicals, USA) was then added to it slowly with stirring and boiling until most of the pseudo-Boehmite dissolved as a colloidal suspension to get solution B. Solution B was then cooled to room temperature and added slowly to solution A with constant vigorous stirring. After the addition of about 60% of solution B, a thick gel formed, which was homogenized by mechanical stirring. The remaining solution B was then added slowly with constant stirring. After the addition was complete, the gel was stirred for at least 30 min to get a homogeneous gel-mix with $\text{pH } 7.46 \pm 0.1$. It was then transferred to a stainless-steel autoclave (300 ml capacity) and the sealed autoclave placed in an air oven maintained at the required temperature. After attaining the temperature, $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, the time was recorded as zeroth hour. At the end of crystallization (40 h), the autoclave was quenched under tap water and cooled to room temperature. The white crystalline solid that settled to the bottom was separated from the supernatant liquid ($\text{pH} = 10.03 \pm 0.1$) by filtration.

The products were removed and washed with deionised water and the sample was dried at $110\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 h. The zeolite so prepared was subjected to various physicochemical characterizations.

X-Ray diffraction patterns were recorded on a Rigaku (D/MAX III VC) instrument in the 2θ region of $5\text{--}50^{\circ}$. Scanning electron microscope pictures were taken using a JEOL JSM 5200 microscope. Chemical analysis was car-

ried out by XRF using a Rigaku 3070 X-ray Spectrometer. TG/DTA analysis was carried out using TG/DTA32 SII Seiko instruments in nitrogen atmosphere from room temperature to $1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The framework IR spectra were recorded in the diffuse reflectance mode using 300:1 ratio sample in KBr (Nicolet 60SXB).

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